

BOLZANO

Popular Financial Report

for Fiscal Year Ended December 31, 2022

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MAYOR'S LETTER

For the year 2022, we propose the Pop report of the city, social reporting that make the citizens closer to the institution through transparent access of information regarding the allocation of resources, urban dynamics and achieved objectives.

Bolzano resulted second in the Sole24ore ranking for the quality of life. Furthermore, the city received an award for the ecological urban transition. The evaluation system of urban ecosystem looked at 105 cities and 30.000 collected data and declared the first place for Bolzano together with Belluno and Trento.

The trend about tourism is in constant growing after 2020 such that the city is trying to develop a sustainable tourism system.

The city started a series of investment to prepare to the winter Olympic games.

The infrastructure investment is at the basis of it. Sustainability is again playing a fundamental role in the management of these actions.

Despite the inflation due to the war and the after-covid recovery Bolzano municipality is able to cope and keep going with these investments with a definite allocation of resources.

Moreover, Bolzano citizens are accompanied by social policies that are run well thanks to the fact that Bolzano is an independent province. Satisfaction is shared by Bolzano's citizens.

Also at financial level the municipality of Bolzano is one of the best performer in Italy.

MUNICIPALITY OF BOLZANO - 31.12.2022

INHABITANTS

107.192

WOMEN

52%

MEN

48%

ITALIAN

85,2%

OTHER NATIONALITIES

14,8%

DISTRIBUTION OF MAJOR AGE GROUPS

0-4 years old	5-14 years old	15-64 years old	65-75 years old	>75 years old
4,1%	9,6%	62,5%	11,4%	12,5%

TRENDS

POPULATION

NATIONALITY

AGE

	0-4	5-14	15-64	65-75	>75
2021	4,2%	9,7%	62,5%	11,5%	12,1%
2022	4,1%	9,6%	62,5%	11,4%	12,5%

Sources:

Andamento e struttura della popolazione di Bolzano e dei suoi quartieri 2023

Andamento e struttura della popolazione di Bolzano e dei suoi quartieri 2022

Situazione definitiva sulla popolazione al 31.12.2020

<https://opencity.comune.bolzano.it/Documenti-e-dati/Progetti-studi-e-ricerche/Statistica-Popolazione-e-societa>

GEOGRAPHICAL CHARACTERISTICS

52,34 km²

Area

5

Districts

2.048 km²

Inhabitants per km²

Source: Opuscolo Bolzano in cifre

2023 ITA con margini

<https://opencity.comune.bolzano.it/Novita/Comunicati-stampa/Andamento-demografico-e-Bolzano-2023-La-citta-in-cifre>

AWARDS AND RECOGNITIONS

World Capital of Time Policies

BOLZANO 2023-24

Bolzano World Capital of Time 2023-2024

Source: <https://opencity.comune.bolzano.it/Novita/Comunicati-stampa/Bolzano-Capitale-del-Tempo-2023-2024>

Interreg
Italia-Österreich
European Regional Development Fund

Spread of tourist inclusiveness for the development of territories

Source: <https://gateproject.dolomitiunesco.info/progetto-gate/work-packages/>

DOLOMITES WORLD HERITAGE GEOTRAIL

Special Award Dolomites UNESCO World Heritage

Source: <https://www.dolomitiunesco.info/attivita/premio-speciale-dolomiti-unesco-2023>

Il Sole **24 ORE**

Classification 2022 - 2° place - Life Quality

Source: <https://lab24.ilsole24ore.com/qualita-della-vita/bolzano>

2022 "BenVivere" Report - 1° place

Source: https://www.ansa.it/ansa2030/notizie/lavoro_formazione/2023/09/30/bolzano-si-conferma-prima-nel-rapporto-benvivere_9a24b0a3-ec54-4246-b4b4-09ea7d826359.html

2022 "BenVivere" Report - 1° place

Source: <https://www.filmfestival.bz.it/it/edizione-2023/premi/deutsch-preise/>

LEGAMBIENTE

2022 "Ecosistema Urbano" Report - 1° place

Source: <https://www.legambiente.it/wp-content/uploads/2022/11/Ecosistema-Urbano-2022.pdf>

2022 "Cycling Municipality" - Maximum Score

Source: <https://opencity.comune.bolzano.it/Novita/Comunicati-stampa/Bolzano-si-conferma-Comune-Ciclabile-a-5-stelle-bike-smile>

CONTEXTUAL CHARACTERISTICS

COMUNE DI BOLZANO

TOURISM

ATTENDANCE PER MONTH - WINTER SEASONS 2017/18 2022/23

Source: Andamento turistico a Bolzano - Stagione invernale 2022-2023

<https://opencity.comune.bolzano.it/Documenti-e-dati/Progetti-studi-e-ricerche/Statistica-Economia-e-turismo>

LIBRARIES

Libraries	Book Heritage	Book Loans	Others Heritage	Others Loans
29	1.345.586	372.915	112.461	64.800

Source: astat info 31/2023 [PDF 928 KB]

https://astat.provincia.bz.it/it/news-pubblicazioni-info.asp?news_action=4&news_article_id=676576

PUBLIC EMPLOYMENT

Total	Public sector (average)
43.527	12.977

Source: Mercato del Lavoro 2019-2022

<https://opencity.comune.bolzano.it/Novita/News/Occupazione-e-disoccupazione-a-Bolzano-nel-2022>

HEALTH & HEALTHCARE

1 Hospital
4 Care facilities
31 Pharmacies

Source: Strutture e prestazioni sanitarie - 2022

<https://opencity.comune.bolzano.it/Documenti-e-dati/Progetti-studi-e-ricerche/Statistica-Sanita-e-sociale>

GREEN AREAS

130 hectares of public greenery

Shrubs studied	Trees studied	CO ₂ seized	PM absorbed	Energy saved
11.423	3.054	78 t	989 Kg	45 MWh

Source: <https://bolzano.verdevale.eu/it/about/>

EDUCATION

Quantity	Level	Enrolled	Universities	Enrolled
46	Kindergartens	2.653	1	Economic Faculty 831
23	Primary School	5.089	1	Computer Science 333
17	Secondary School	3.492	1	Arts and Design 322
19	High School	9.068	1	Sciences and Technologies 636

The Free University of Bolzano was established on 31 October 1997 as a multilingual university with an international vocation. It is a non-state institution authorized to issue degrees pursuant to the law of 7 August 1990, n. 245, article 6, paragraph 1.

Source: <https://opencity.comune.bolzano.it/Documenti-e-dati/Progetti-studi-e-ricerche/Statistica-Istruzione-e-cultura>

THE PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION GROUP

SHAREHOLDINGS

SUBSIDIARY COMPANIES

PARTICIPATED COMPANIES (SUBSIDIARIES)

Alperia 21%	Eco Center Spa 43,86%	Alto Adige Riscossioni Spa 4,10%	Areale Bolzano ABZ Spa 50%	Fiera di Bolzano Spa 4,6%
Unifarm Spa 1,33%	Banca Popolare Etica Scpa 0,0032%	Autostrada del Brennero Spa 4,23%	SASA SpA 6,33%	Consorzio dei Comuni della Provincia di Bolzano Società cooperativa 0,813%

CONTROLLED COMPANIES (AFFILIATES)

SEAB Servizi Energia Ambiente Bolzano Spa 99%	Funivia del Colle Srl 100%
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PRIVATE LAW ENTITIES

Associazione Vereinigte Bühnen Bozen 20%	Fondazione Castelli di Bolzano 100%
Fondazione Ferruccio Busoni - Gustav Mahler 80%	Fondazione Haydn di Bolzano e Trento 20%
Fondazione Teatro Comunale e Auditorium 50%	

PUBLIC SUPERVISED BODIES

Azienda Servizi Sociali di Bolzano 100%
Ente Autonomo Magazzini generali di Bolzano 30%
Teatro Stabile di Bolzano 60%

Data at 2022

Source: Allegato B - Relazione al Bilancio Consolidato 2022
<https://opencity.comune.bolzano.it/Amministrazione-Trasparente/Bilanci/Bilancio-consolidato/Bilancio-consolidato-2022>

NUMBER OF EMPLOYEES (FTE) - FUNCTIONS

Proportional number of employees calculation based on the controlling entity's percentage of participation in the controlled entity

Institution	N. Employees	Function	Institution	N. Employees	Function
bancaetica	0,013	Savings and credit with ethic purposes			
STIFTUNG BOZNER SCHLÖSSER FONDAZIONE CASTELLI DI BOLZANO	10,26	Castles and cultural heritage management			
MG MAGAZZINI GENERALI DI BOLZANO ALLGEMEINES LAGERHAUS BOZEN	2,4	General stores inside and outside the city			
ASSB-BSB	916,67	Well-being of citizens management			
VEREINIGTE BÜHNEN BOZEN	4,2	Cultural activities in German language			
Autostrada del Brennero SpA Brennerautobahn AG	38,28	Highway management	HADN FONDAZIONE ARON STIFUNG	39,2	Cultural music promotion
FUNIVIA DEL COLLE Società a partecipazione pubblica	3	Bolzano-Colle ski lift operation			
unifarm	5,11	Wholesale medicines, pharmacy and public health services			
se ab	276,21	Water, gas, energy, waste, other business utilities management			
FERRUCCIO BUSONI GUSTAV MAHLER	2,4	Classical music events and classes			
teatro stabile di bolzano	15,6	Cultural activities in Italian language			

PERCENTAGES

MUNICIPALITY EMPLOYEES

Data at 31.12.2022

TOTAL	982
PERMANENT CONTRACT	928
FIXED-TERM CONTRACT	54
MALE	453
FEMALE	529

EMPLOYEES CITY OF BOLZANO AND LOCAL PUBLIC GROUP

Local Public Group	2,5%
Employed	40,61%
Inhabitants	107.192

Sources: Allegato B - Relazione al Bilancio Consolidato 2022

<https://opencity.comune.bolzano.it/Amministrazione-Trasparente/Bilanci/Bilancio-consolidato/Bilancio-consolidato-2022>

Società Partecipate al 31.12.2022 / Enti diritto privato al 31.12.22 / Enti pubblici vigilati al 31.12.22

<https://opencity.comune.bolzano.it/Amministrazione/Enti-e-societa-partecipati>

Dipendenti Comune ITA.doc

<https://opencity.comune.bolzano.it/Documenti-e-dati/Progetti-studi-e-ricerche/Statistica-Amministrazione-comunale>

CITY GOVERNANCE

2022

MUNICIPAL COUNCIL

45 MEMBERS
9 POLITICAL PARTIES

63 SESSIONS
57 INQUIRIES

41 MOTIONS PRESENTED - 5 APPROVED
4 INTERPELLATIONS

Sources: <https://opencity.comune.bolzano.it/Documenti-e-dati/Documenti-funzionamento-interno/Documento-unico-di-programmazione-DUP-2022-2024>
<https://opencity.comune.bolzano.it/Documenti-e-dati/Attivita-Consiglio-Comunale#122>
<https://opencity.comune.bolzano.it/Documenti-e-dati/Attivita-Consiglio-Comunale/09.10.2023-Riepilogo-situazione-mozioni>

COUNCIL COMMITTEES

PERSONNEL

GENERAL AFFAIRS,
ORGANIZATION,
INFORMATION
TECHNOLOGY, SMART
CITY, INNOVATION,
TRANSPARENCY AND
LEGALITY

President: Giovannetti Gabriele

Members: Albani Andrea, Benedikter Rudolf, Cologna Matthias, Forest Alessandro, Hristov Mirche, Huber della Torre di Valsassina Alessandro, Warasin Peter

Alternates: Baratta Silvano, Bonomini Monica, Brancaglioni Thomas, Buratti Christoph, Chniouli Abdallah, Della Ratta Claudio, Pancheri Kurt, Scarafoni Anna, Schönsberg Primo

YOUTH AND
COMMUNITY
DEVELOPMENT

President: Planer Tobias

Members: Bonomini Monica, Chniouli Abdallah, Cologna Matthias, Franch Monica, Selle Roberto, Seppi Walter, Stagni Stefano, Unterhofer Hannes

Alternates: Abrate Sonia, Borgo Davide, Brancaglioni Thomas, Caruso Marco Della Ratta, Claudio Huber della Torre di Valsassina Alessandro, Myftiu Tritan, Warasin Peter

DECENTRALISATION,
DEMOGRAPHIC,
PERSONNEL, STATISTICS
AND CITY TIME SERVICES

President: Baratta Silvano

Vicepresident: Pegoraro Barbara

Members: Abrate Sonia, Buratti Christoph, Caruso Marco, Franch Monica, Myftiu Tritan, Schönsberg Primo, Stagni Stefano

Alternates: Bonomini Monica, Borgo Davide, Borgo Pietro, Della Ratta Claudio, Giovannetti Gabriele, Pancheri Kurt, Planer Tobias, Scarafoni Anna, Unterhofer Hannes

EQUAL OPPORTUNITY

President: Chiara Rabini

Vicepresident: Baroncelli Stefania

Members: Abrate Sonia, Bonomini Monica, Brillo Patrizia, Franch Monica, Pegoraro Barbara, Johanna Ramoser, Scarafoni Anna

ENVIRONMENT

President: Berger Andreas

Vicepresident: Della Ratta Claudio

Members: Abrate Sonia, Baroncelli Stefania, Borgo Davide, Caruso Marco, Myftiu Tritan, Schönsberg Primo, Selle Roberto

Alternates: Albani Andrea, Chniouli Abdallah, Franch Monica, Lantschner Norbert, Pancheri Kurt, Repetto Gabriele, Seppi Walter, Stagni Stefano, Unterhofer Hannes

<p>ADMINISTRATION OF FINANCIAL RESOURCES</p>	<p>President: Borgo Davide Vicepresident: Della Ratta Claudio Members: Abrate Sonia, Baratta Silvano, Baroncelli Stefania, Forest Alessandro, Giovannetti Gabriele, Pancheri Kurt, Unterhofer Hannes Alternates: Berger Andreas, Bonomini Monica, Borgo Pietro, Hristov Mirche, Huber della Torre di Valsassina Alessandro, Myftiu Tritan, Pegoraro Barbara, Planer Tobias, Zanin Roberto</p>
<p>ECONOMICAL ACTIVITIES TOURISM STADTMARKETING</p>	<p>President: Benedikter Rudolf Members: Borgo Pietro, Brillo Patrizia, Huber della Torre di Valsassina Alessandro, Repetto Gabriele, Scarafoni Anna, Unterhofer Hannes, Zanin Roberto, Zine Sekali Samir Alternates: Baroncelli Stefania, Berger Andreas, Chniouli Abdallah, Della Ratta Claudio, Hristov Mirche, Myftiu Tritan, Nevola Luigi, Planer Tobias, Schönsberg Primo</p>
<p>SOCIAL ACTIVITIES AND SPORT</p>	<p>President: Buratti Christoph Vicepresident: Scarafoni Anna Members: Baratta Silvano, Pegoraro Barbara, Planer Tobias, Schönsberg Primo, Selle Roberto, Zanin Roberto, Zine Sekali Samir Alternates: Abrate Sonia, Albani Andrea, Bonomini Monica, Della Ratta Claudio, Huber della Torre di Valsassina Alessandro, Pancheri Kurt, Seppi Walter, Stagni Stefano, Unterhofer Hannes</p>
<p>CULTURE</p>	<p>President: Huber della Torre di Valsassina Alessandro Vicepresident: Giovannetti Gabriele Members: Berger Andreas, Brancaglion Thomas, Chniouli Abdallah, Della Ratta Claudio, Planer Tobias, Scarafoni Anna, Schönsberg Primo Alternates: Abrate Sonia, Baratta Silvano, Borgo Davide, Borgo Pietro, Brillo Patrizia, Buratti Christoph, Myftiu Tritan, Nevola Luigi, Selle Roberto</p>
<p>PUBLIC WORKS AND CIVIL PROTECTION</p>	<p>President: Lantschner Norbert Vicepresident: Della Ratta Claudio Members: Baratta Silvano, Bonomini Monica, Selle Roberto, Seppi Walter, Stagni Stefano, Warasin Peter, Zine Sekali Samir Alternates: Abrate Sonia, Baroncelli Stefania, Borgo Pietro, Chniouli Abdallah, Cologna Matthias, Forest Alessandro, Huber della Torre di Valsassina Alessandro, Pancheri Kurt, Pegoraro Barbara</p>
<p>MOBILITY</p>	<p>President: Abrate Sonia Vicepresident: Forest Alessandro Members: Borgo Pietro, Caruso Marco, Della Ratta Claudio, Hristov Mirche, Huber della Torre di Valsassina Alessandro, Warasin Peter, Zine Sekali Samir Alternates: Baratta Silvano, Benedikter Rudolf, Borgo Davide, Cologna Matthias, Franch Monica, Myftiu Tritan, Repetto Gabriele, Schönsberg Primo, Seppi Walter</p>
<p>NOMINATIONS</p>	<p>President: Borgo Pietro Vicepresident: Baroncelli Stefania Members: Brancaglion Thomas, Buratti Christoph, Giovannetti Gabriele, Huber della Torre di Valsassina Alessandro, Pancheri Kurt, Planer Tobias</p>
<p>HONOURS</p>	<p>Mayor: Renzo Caramaschi Vicemayor: Luis Walcher Members: Repetto Gabriele, Schönsberg Primo, Seppi Walter, Warasin Peter Alternates: Giovannetti Gabriele, Hristov Mirche, Huber della Torre di Valsassina Alessandro, Planer Tobias</p>

<p>ASSETS, EXPROPRIATIONS AND MUNICIPAL HOUSING</p>	<p>President: Unterhofer Hannes Vicepresident: Cologna Matthias Members: Benedikter Rudolf, Bonomini Monica, Brillo Patrizia, Chniouli Abdallah, Pegoraro Barbara, Schönsberg Primo, Stagni Stefano, Alternates: Abrate Sonia, Baratta Silvano, Berger Andreas, Borgo Davide, Borgo Pietro, Della Ratta Claudio, Hristov Mirche, Myftiu Tritan, Repetto Gabriele</p>
<p>TERRITORY DEVELOPEMENT</p>	<p>President: Bonomini Monica Vicepresident: Giovannetti Gabriele Members: Baratta Silvano, Berger Andreas, Borgo Pietro, Lantschner Norbert, Pancheri Kurt, Repetto Gabriele, Stagni Stefano Alternates: Benedikter Rudolf, Borgo Davide, Caruso Marco, Della Ratta Claudio, Forest Alessandro, Pegoraro Barbara, Schönsberg Primo, Warasin Peter, Zine Sekali Samir</p>
<p>SCHOOL AND EXTRACURRICULAR ACTIVITIES, FAMILY AND LEISURE</p>	<p>President: Chniouli Abdallah Vicepresident: Scarafoni Anna Members: Abrate Sonia, Borgo Pietro, Buratti Christoph, Franch Monica, Nevola Luigi, Pancheri Kurt, Seppi Walter Alternates: Bonomini Monica, Borgo Davide, Brillo Patrizia, Della Ratta Claudio, Hristov Mirche, Myftiu Tritan, Planer Tobias, Schönsberg Primo, Warasin Peter</p>

Source: <https://opencity.comune.bolzano.it/Amministrazione/Organi-di-governo-2020-2025/Consiglio-comunale/Commissioni-consiliari>

RANKING AND POSITIONING

By **Sole24Ore** Bolzano results is 2nd out of 107 Italian provinces in the quality of life ranking, in 2022.

Ranking		Var.22/21	Province	Score	Medals
1		+5 ▲	Bologna	590,28	
2		+3 ▲	Bolzano	585,73	
3		+8 ▲	Firenze	581,86	
4		+11 ▲	Siena	578,52	
5		-2 ▼	Trento	576,62	
6		-2 ▼	Aosta	575,38	
7		-6 ▼	Trieste	574,35	
8		-6 ▼	Milano	573,94	
9		+3 ▲	Parma	573,82	
10		+12 ▲	Pisa	567,93	

The analysis is based on 6 parameters that analyse the followings indicators:

- Wealth and consumption
- Business and work
- Justice and security
- Demography and society
- Environment and services
- Culture and leisure

	2019	2020	2021	2022
Wealth and consumption	51°	33°	7°	3° ↑
Business and work	3°	5°	15°	24° ↓
Justice and security	28°	30°	29°	27° ↑
Demography and society	1°	5°	16°	11° ↑
Environment and services	3°	27°	6°	4° ↑
Culture and leisure	30°	42°	28°	21° ↑

La graduatoria completa

RANKING ICR 2022											
RANK	COMUNE	PUNTEGGIO	RANK	COMUNE	PUNTEGGIO	RANK	COMUNE	PUNTEGGIO	RANK	COMUNE	PUNTEGGIO
1	Firenze	90	28	Messina	67	55	Catania	56	81	Belluno	42
2	Milano	87	28	Treviso	67	55	Lecco	56	83	Trapani	40
3	Bergamo	85	30	Bolzano	66	55	Vercelli	56	83	Teramo	40
3	Bologna	85	30	Cuneo	66	58	Alessandria	55	83	Potenza	40
3	Cremona	85	32	Ferrara	65	59	Ancona	54	83	Caltanissetta	40
3	Modena	85	32	Napoli	65	59	Matera	54	83	Brindisi	40
3	Roma Capitale	85	32	Pavia	65	61	L'Aquila	53	83	Viterbo	40
3	Trento	85	32	Piacenza	65	61	Lucca	53	83	Savona	40
9	Cagliari	82	36	Livorno	64	63	Reggio Calabria	51	83	Latina	40
9	Genova	82	36	Pescara	64	63	Sondrio	51	91	Biella	39
11	Parma	78	36	Ravenna	64	65	Andria	50	92	Siracusa	38
11	Torino	78	39	Arezzo	63	65	Terni	50	92	Ragusa	38
13	Brescia	76	40	Novara	62	67	Imperia	48	94	Nuoro	37
13	Venezia	76	41	Lodi	61	67	Grosseto	48	94	Frosinone	37
15	Palermo	75	41	Perugia	61	67	Vibo Valentia	48	96	Caserta	36
15	Prato	75	41	Trieste	61	67	Sassari	48	96	Salerno	36
15	Reggio Emilia	75	44	La Spezia	60	71	Campobasso	47	98	Carbonia	35
15	Rimini	75	44	Mantova	60	71	Ascoli Piceno	47	99	Cosenza	33
15	Verona	75	44	Pordenone	60	73	Pistoia	46	99	Crotone	33
20	Bari	74	44	Udine	60	73	Macerata	46	99	Chieti	33
20	Cesena	74	48	Aosta	59	73	Como	46	102	Rieti	28
20	Pisa	74	41	Forli	59	73	Oristano	46	103	Avellino	27
23	Padova	73	50	Massa	58	73	Gorizia	46	103	Benevento	27
24	Lecce	70	51	Asti	57	78	Varese	45	105	Foggia	26
24	Siena	70	51	Pesaro	57	79	Taranto	44	106	Agrigento	22
24	Vicenza	70	51	Rovigo	57	80	Catanzaro	43	107	Enna	20
27	Monza	69	51	Verbania	57	81	Fermo	42	108	Isernia	15

IOT and network technologies: system of urban functional services, in particular traffic light network, waste collection, public lighting, infomobility and greenery management. Bolzano is in first place on a par with other 6 cities.

Human smart city index 2022, by EY

	Ranking nazionale	Punteggio	Readiness	Comportamenti	Transiz. Ecologica	Transiz. Digitale	Inclusione Sociale e Attrattività	Ranking nazionale 2020
Milano	1	85,25						1
Bologna	2	84,00						3
Torino	3	78,96						2
Trento	4	71,54						5
Parma	5	71,41						9
Bergamo	6	70,71						6
Padova	7	68,56						16
Brescia	8	68,09						10
Venezia	9	68,05						13
Firenze	10	67,01						8
Modena	11	66,30						4
Roma	12	64,27						7
Ferrara	13	63,95						20
Genova	14	62,61						10
Trieste	15	61,67						33
Bolzano	16	61,64						19
Rimini	17	61,63						15
Ravenna	18	61,19						17
Cagliari	19	61,11						21
La Spezia	20	60,40						14

Readiness: ability of stakeholders to redesign the city on the needs of citizens.

Behavior: overall attitude of the citizens.

Ecological transaction: sustainable mobility, energy efficiency, sustainable environment.

Digital transaction: digital infrastructures, service ecosystems, digital platforms, incubators, co-working, research centers.

Social inclusion and attractiveness: listening, eparticipation, digital engagement (social network), social policies (social budget, expenses, online services), health services.

POLICIES

1. Smart city policies

1.1. Smart Specialization Strategy (RIS3) of the Autonomous Province of Bolzano

file:///C:/Users/Elena/Downloads/Smart%20Specialisation%20Strategy%20(RIS3).pdf

Research and innovation program that sets the local priorities and conditions for innovation and technology transfer

Optimize the use of structural funds and enhance cooperation between different policy areas at European, national, and regional levels, as well as between public and private investments

Establishment of a monitoring system to inform decision-making and resource allocation.

Focus on South Tyrol specific strategic strengths as an innovation hub and involve local stakeholders through a participatory process.

1.2. Sinfonia project

Five-year project that aims to transform certain areas of Bolzano and make the city a European model for sustainable energy management.

3 main goals

Energy retrofit of **450 social housing** which will **reduce energy consumption** in the entire area **by over 50%** compared to the current levels

Improvement of the district heating system

Installation of "smart points" - **150 stations** that monitor climate, air quality, and traffic, while also providing services like electric vehicle charging.

2. European projects

2.1. EUROPE DIRECT Alto Adige

EUROPE DIRECT
Südtirol · Alto Adige

Tap on the image to know more

The project represents the point of contact between the population and the European Union (EU). The province of Bolzano informs about European issues and promote dialogue on EU issues, offering easy, free and personal access to information about the EU. People can contact the office with a telephone number and an email address present on the official website of Bolzano.

2.2. Initiatives dedicated to the schools of Bolzano to spread the knowledge about the European Union

- Crossing Europe - initiative for elementary schools and middle schools
- First steps in Europe - training course for elementary schools
- Introduction to community information on the web - training course for middle schools, high schools and universities
- EU regional policy - training course for middle schools, high schools and universities.

2.3. European funds

In Alto Adige, the European structural funds finance the programs European Regional Development Fund (ERDF), European Social Fund Plus (ESF+), Interreg VI-A Italy - Austria and the Rural Development Programme.

3. Social policies and assistance

By analysing the social policy we must consider the poverty level in Bolzano. By [Istat data](#) we can see that Bolzano has a low relative poverty level with respect to other Italian regions. This is due to the fact that being an independent province Bolzano is able to cope with social issues in a more effective way. The efficiency is due also to the social policies that will be described.

Tipo dato	incidenza di povertà relativa individuale (% di persone che vivono in famiglie in povertà relativa sui residenti)		
Seleziona periodo	2019	2020	2021
Territorio			
Italia	14.7	13.5	14.8
Nord	8.7	8.7	9
Nord-ovest	9.1	9.3	8.9
Piemonte	10.5	8.9	10.2
Valle d'Aosta / Vallée d'Aoste	4.9	6.9	3.8
Liguria	12.6	10.5	10.2
Lombardia	8	9.3	8.2
Nord-est	8.1	7.9	9.2
Trentino Alto Adige / Südtirol	5.3	5.6	6.1
Provincia Autonoma Bolzano / Bozen	3.4	3.5	5.3
Provincia Autonoma Trento	7.2	7.7	6.9
Veneto	11.5	8.2	10.4

Some data to highlights the importance of the social assistance.

Users of ASSB (Agenzia dei servizi sociali di Bolzano) and the expenses.

Old people	31.986.397,00 €
Socio-economic assistance	21.706.910,00 €
Disable people	13.157.537,00 €
Minors and family	9.558.892,00 €
Early childhood	8,810.332,00 €
Interventions for adults	6.150.421,00 €
Others	5.317.859,15
TOT	96.688.348,15 €

Some of the most important social expenses by the province of Bolzano of the biennium 2022-2024.

file:///C:/Users/Elena/Downloads/Budgetpolitichesociali2022-2024.pdf

	2022	2023	2024
Care allowance	241.584.266,59 €	272.000.000,00 €	272.000.000,00 €
Civil disabled, blind and deaf	€ 32.951.000,00	€ 18.710.870,49	€ 18.642.514,00
Provincial allowance to the family unit	€ 33.051.000,00	€ 18.710.870,49	€ 18.642.514,00
Provincial child allowance	€ 11.963.486,00	€ 11.963.486,00	€ 11.963.486,00
State allowance for the family unit	€ 600.000,00	-	-
State maternity allowance	€ 220.000,00	-	-
TOT	320.369.752,59 €	321.385.226,98 €	321.248.514,00 €

Example of social assistance in Bolzano:

- Request municipally owned housing for particular social categories
- Apply for municipal sheltered housing for the elderly. there are **40 houses** destined for this purpose.

19,7% of the population is composed by people +65 years old. policy must consider this data and provide adequate measures, as the one described.

4. Family policies

- Taxi voucher that give a **discount of 3 to 5 euros** for each ride. Also for old people and women travelling alone.
- "Baby pack" for every newborn.
- Family card giving discounts and advantages.
- Possibility of requesting a contribution for the purchase of washable diapers

828 newborns in 2022 who received the "Baby pack" including:

- A backpack for children
- A bath towel with hood
- An information brochure of the Province "Welcome baby - Useful information for parents"
- A first pack of booklets to read to newborns.

Single-person families

Families with kids

As we see the number of family with kids decreased in 2022, as the rest in Italy in the last years. This is why it is important that Bolzano introduce families policies, as the one previously described.

file:///C:/Users/Elena/Downloads/DatiBolzano2022.pdf

5. Immigration policies

- Project CA-MM-INI: Meetings of discussion and participation in social and cultural life by migrant associations and valorisation of cultures and promotion of intercultural dialogue.
- "Educate, Inform, Live": to promote and encourage intercultural dialogue with **130 immigrants** people and **40 local organisations** involved.
- Project HNT0: support initiatives for women and young people from third countries, financed by the Minister of Labor and Social Policies which provides **500,000 euros**.

Out of the total population of Bolzano, 14,8% are immigrants, so it is important to have policies for their integration and active participation in the community. In 2022 **594 immigrants** acquired the Italian **citizenship**.

file:///C:/Users/Elena/Downloads/DatiBolzano2022.pdf

6. Equal opportunities

- “Empowerment for women” help desk: carry out actions of female empowerment, meet and listen to women, in their needs, desires and expectations, and enhance their multiple skills. It works to affirm every woman's right to citizenship and self-determination: the right to be present, in work, in society, in culture and in politics.
- YOU help desk: sexual orientation and gender counseling service.
- RE.A.DY network: the project develop positive actions in the area and encourage the implementation of the rights and equal opportunities of people with a different sexual orientation.

48,2%

51,8%

In Bolzano there are more females than males.

As regard homosexual people 4,3% of people in stable relationships declared to have partner of the same gender.

file:///C:/Users/Elena/Downloads/Omosessualit%C3%A0inBolzano.pdf

file:///C:/Users/Elena/Downloads/DatiBolzano2022.pdf

7. Youth projects

- FUTURA project: it supports the artistic talent of the under 35 of Bolzano by making available to them for a week the Municipal Theatre of Gries to set up and stage in front of the public, an artistic work.
- Youth Restart: festival where young people can set up laboratories, play sports, and other activities.
- 39C Bolzano Graffiti Jam: 80 international artists will create graffiti on the boundary wall of the Valbruna steelworks.

Approximately there are 12.000 young people that can join these projects.

Popolazione per età, sesso e stato civile - 2021

COMUNE DI BOLZANO - Dati ISTAT 1° gennaio 2021 - Elaborazione TUTTITALIA.IT

8. Sustainable mobility policy

“Green mobility” project: developing Alto Adige as a model region for sustainable Alpine mobility and deals with all forms of sustainable transport and their coordination. In addition to ensuring a good urban public transport system, sustainable mobility must be developed so that South Tyrol maintains a high quality of life, increases its tourist attractiveness, stimulates economic competitiveness and contributes to mobilizing new technological. To achieve these objectives, Green Mobility focuses above all on electric and intermodal mobility, and on bicycle mobility.

	SPOSTAMENTI PER STUDIO (a)		SPOSTAMENTI PER LAVORO (b)	
	Provincia Autonoma Bolzano/Bozen	Italia	Provincia Autonoma Bolzano/Bozen	Italia
Vanno a piedi	39,2	27,5	21,3	12,0
Usano mezzi di trasporto	60,8	72,5	78,7	88,0
Treno	9,5	6,2	4,7	3,3
Tram, bus	15,4	13,0	4,7	4,9
Metropolitana (c)	0,5	4,1	0,0	3,3
Pullman, corriera	13,5	11,6	5,6	1,6
Pullman aziendale	9,0	3,9	0,4	0,3
Auto privata (come conducente)	0,0	4,7	54,2	69,7
Auto privata (come passeggero)	12,8	36,9	7,7	5,6
Motocicletta, ciclomotore	0,4	1,4	1,7	3,4
Bicicletta	9,6	2,2	9,1	3,4
Tempo impiegato				
Fino a 15 minuti	58,2	56,6	50,2	35,8
31 minuti e più	16,5	14,6	10,0	16,6

Fonte: Istat, Indagine multiscopo sulle famiglie "Aspetti della vita quotidiana"

Sustainable mobility projects are important because by the graph we deduce that 54% of the working population is using the car. This number is not so high with respect to other Italian cities but it can be reduced.

9. Waste management policy

SEAB is the entity in charge of the waste collection system in Bolzano.

file:///C:/Users/Elena/Downloads/Wastepolicy2022.pdf

Percentage of separate collection by SEAB

Kg of plastic packages collected

People in Bolzano is more aware about the importance of recycling plastic. Indeed 2,796 tons of plastic packaging were collected in 2022: + 6.6% compared to 2021, and + 23% compared to 2019;

“Iwasteless” project: In September 2020, the Province of Bolzano launched, with the motto #iosprecomeno, an awareness and information campaign against food waste. From the numerous budgets of the technical committee, after two years Bolzano results to be on the right way.

10. Tourism policy

Tourism in South Tyrol has increased exponentially in the last fifteen years. In 2022, the number of tourists (the number of overnight stays) exceeded that of 2019, reaching 34.3 million. Too many, compared to the number of residents. in particular the graph shows the summer permanence in the period 2016-2022.

file:///C:/Users/Elena/Downloads/AndamentoturisticoBolzano2022.pdf

Observatory for sustainable tourism in South Tyrol created a Tourism Exposure Index, that is a set of indicators that classify the tourist score of the cities and set a limit on the number of beds available for tourists. The aim of the Observatory is to guide policies to promote sustainable development and tourism to preserve the environment and reduce the pollution in in the city center of Bolzano.

11. Green and green areas policies

- Green plan of the Municipality of Bolzano of 2022: instrument for urban planning, which determines an organic program of interventions for the quantitative and qualitative development of the urban and naturalistic green in the medium and long term, in line with economic development-social and urban transformation of the municipal territory.
- Programme of the European Regional Development Fund (FERS) 2021-2027 of the Autonomous Province of Bolzano includes Priority 2 "GREEN", which provides as Specific Objective 2.1 to promote energy efficiency and reduce greenhouse gas emissions.

CLASSIFICA FINALE ECOSISTEMA URBANO 2022

Pos.	Città		Pos.	Città		Pos.	Città	
1	Bolzano	79,02%	36	Varese	58,06%	71	Ascoli Piceno	49,00%
2	Trento	76,31%	37	Vicenza	57,70%	72	Pavia	48,17%
3	Belluno	73,74%	38	Milano	57,61%	73	Asti	48,13%
4	Reggio Emilia	72,99%	39	Teramo	57,52%	74	Frosinone	47,98%
5	Cosenza	72,79%	40	Pesaro	57,39%	75	Lecce	47,68%
6	Treviso	72,27%	41	Oristano	57,32%	76	Benevento	47,29%
7	Pordenone	72,00%	42	Livorno	57,03%	77	Prato	47,07%
8	Forlì	70,34%	43	Firenze	56,20%	78	L'Aquila	46,86%
9	La Spezia	67,89%	44	Piacenza	55,92%	79	Brindisi	46,35%
10	Mantova	67,28%	45	Aosta	55,35%	80	Enna	46,33%
11	Rimini	67,00%	46	Vibo Valentia	55,16%	81	Chieti	46,29%
12	Siena	65,43%	47	Novara	54,93%	82	Grosseto	46,14%
13	Venezia	65,05%	48	Matera	54,57%	83	Verona	46,09%
14	Parma	64,94%	49	Modena	54,38%	84	Monza	45,32%
15	Trieste	64,82%	50	Savona	53,49%	85	Bari	44,94%
16	Cuneo	64,15%	51	Rieti	53,44%	86	Pescara	44,52%
17	Ferrara	64,03%	52	Ravenna	53,29%	87	Campobasso	44,39%
18	Udine	63,66%	53	Genova	53,09%	88	Roma	43,85%
19	Perugia	63,31%	54	Lecco	52,91%	89	Nuoro	43,74%
20	Verbania	62,63%	55	Bergamo	52,23%	90	Caltanissetta	43,26%
21	Cremona	62,11%	56	Pisa	52,02%	91	Reggio Calabria	41,82%
22	Macerata	62,03%	57	Potenza	51,80%	92	Napoli	41,17%
23	Cagliari	61,99%	58	Agrigento	51,60%	93	Foggia	40,88%
24	Bologna	61,93%	59	Taranto	51,46%	94	Rovigo	40,73%
25	Terni	61,91%	60	Como	51,07%	95	Pistoia	40,72%
26	Ancona	61,48%	61	Trapani	50,91%	96	Siracusa	39,03%
27	Lucca	61,43%	62	Sassari	50,63%	97	Massa	38,41%
28	Sondrio	60,46%	63	Catanzaro	50,20%	98	Messina	37,65%
29	Padova	60,33%	64	Viterbo	50,14%	99	Salerno	36,54%
30	Gorizia	59,64%	65	Torino	49,95%	100	Crotone	36,11%
31	Arezzo	59,60%	66	Ragusa	49,95%	101	Isernia	34,99%
32	Biella	59,49%	67	Caserta	49,63%	102	Latina	33,79%
33	Cesena	59,02%	68	Vercelli	49,19%	103	Alessandria	32,24%
34	Brescia	58,98%	69	Avellino	49,04%	104	Palermo	25,95%
35	Lodi	58,60%	70	Imperia	49,03%	105	Catania	21,94%

Fonte: Legambiente, Ecosistema Urbano (Comuni, dati 2021)
Elaborazione: Ambiente Italia

The classification is based on 5 macro-areas indicated with the following colors:

- Air
- Water
- Waste
- Mobility
- Environment

Tap on the image if you want to know more

12. Sport projects

Sportpertutti: the aim is to rewriting the sports proposal, redesigning the activity of each discipline "to your own measure" around the profile of each, bringing to light the profile of the UISP: the culture of rights, the environment, solidarity.

8.0.1 Sport service:

- Promotion of sporting activities
- Management of activities at sports facilities
- Organization of sporting events
- Grants for activities and events in the sector and sponsorship
- Legislation and measures in the sector

Bolzano is already at a good point as redard the practice of sport. In 2021of the population declared to practice sport regularly. South Tyrol is the most sporting territory in Italy.

Attività sportiva in Italia e Alto Adige 1997-2021 (fonte: ISTAT)

13. Security and public order

The entities in charge are the Municipal policy and the Civil protection.

Crime index 2023 by Istat

- 2019 > 75°
- 2020 > 68°
- 2021 > 75°
- 2022 > 74°
- 2023 > 56°

2022
↓
14.581
complaints

2023
↓
16.258
complaints

Criminality in Bolzano Increase in the last year, escalating the rank. The main complaints in 2023 are:

Theft	7.558
Scams and computer fraud	1.238
Damages	1.078
Intentional injuries	556
Threats	507

INTELLECTUAL CAPITAL

1. **Knowledge and Education:** Bolzano boasts an array of educational institutions, including the renowned Free University of Bozen-Bolzano. These institutions serve as hubs of knowledge and learning, attracting students and scholars from around the world. The diverse academic and research programs offered contribute to the city's intellectual capital by fostering innovation and cultural exchange. In 2022, €15.7 million of external funding have been recovered. The university has established some partnerships, as the collaboration with World Manufacturing Foundation. Moreover in collaboration with the NOI Techpark Business Incubator, the university accompanies the creation of start-ups and spin-offs with strong links to university research.

300 research projects

More than 450 professors and researchers engaged

8 doctoral programmes

2. **Culture:** Bolzano is famous for its lively cultural scene. Cultural events, art exhibitions and events are an integral part of city life, promoting art and creativity. The intellectual capital of Bolzano is also reflected in the numerous libraries, historical archives and museums that preserve and promote the history and culture of the region.

Number of visits for museum type in 2021 by ASTAT.

Heritage and book loans for community district in 2021 by ASTAT.

file:///C:/Users/Elena/Downloads/CulturainBolzano.pdf

In 2022 the “book culture” is increasing by datas of the libraries of Bolzano.

3. Innovation and Entrepreneurship: The city has developed a thriving entrepreneurial ecosystem, thanks in part to its intellectual capital. The cross-pollination of ideas and access to a highly educated workforce have spurred the growth of startups and innovative businesses in various sectors, ranging from technology and renewable energy to sustainable agriculture. Intellectual property, such as patents and proprietary technologies, plays a pivotal role in establishing Bolzano as a hub for innovative entrepreneurship. Companies can directly benefit from the university of Bolzano research results and innovative technologies.

Some innovation are the following spin-off: ONTOPIC and AIAQUA.

ONTOPIC has the aim of enabling organizations to understand and use their data.

AIAQUA offers an innovative solution for the efficient and sustainable management of small and medium-sized water supply systems.

Then we must mention the IIT Institute for technology innovation of Bolzano. Since 2006, IIT has been mainly involved in the development of hydrogen technology in South Tyrol and has been able to accumulate a vast amount of experience in the field of zero emission mobility and hydrogen technology in particular.

4. Multilingual and Multiculturalism: Bolzano's unique position as a bilingual city, where both Italian and German are official languages, underscores its intellectual diversity. This linguistic and cultural richness fosters the exchange of ideas and perspectives, making it an ideal environment for creativity and innovation.

5. Research and Development: The city's investment in research and development is a testament to its commitment to intellectual capital. Bolzano has become a hub for research initiatives, especially in fields related to the Alpine environment, climate change, and sustainable development. One of the most important research entity is the Institute for the Alpine Environment.

eurac research

ISTITUTO PER L'AMBIENTE ALPINO

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HUMAN CAPITAL

1. Education and training

2. Multilingualism

3. **Health and Quality of Life:** Bolzano's commitment to a high quality of life and well-being plays a significant role in its economic development, as a intangible asset. The region's pristine Alpine environment, combined with a strong focus on sustainability and health, results in a healthy and motivated population in the work place. Healthy individuals contribute to greater productivity and a lower burden on healthcare systems, further enhancing Bolzano's economic vitality.

People who feel healthy by age group. Comparison 2016-2019 and 2020-2021

4. Work Ethic and Loyalty: Bolzano's workforce is known for its strong work ethic, punctuality, and loyalty to employers. These qualities are highly valued by businesses and contribute to increased efficiency, reduced turnover, and a sense of stability within the workforce. The dedication and loyalty of Bolzano's labor force are critical components of the region's economic human capital. A specification must be done, indeed after the pandemic crisis the autonomous resignation increased. Either way Bolzano's workforce is still one of the most loyal and trained.

Daily monitoring of employment 2019-October 2023

Redundancies 2019-October 2023

Resignations 2019-October 2023

Tap if you want to know more

Dati mercato del lavoro online
| Lavoro | Provincia autonoma di Bolzano - Alto Adige
 provincia.bz.it

CONSOLIDATED FINANCIAL STATEMENT

• *What is it?* It is a financial statement that shows the economic, equity and financial condition of a group of companies, considered as one only company.

• *Who does it consider?*

1. The balance of the city

2. The balance of the societies that are controlled (Bolzano owns >50% shares, so it can influence the administration of the society and its administrators) and connected (Bolzano owns an insufficient number of shares to directly influence the administration of the societies, but it can take part in the decision making activities).

3. The balance of non profit entities that are controlled (Associations, Foundations, Cooperatives, consortia)

Some data...

Financial results of Bolzano are great, starting from its main bank group, *Sparkasse* team, that has been awarded as the bank with the lowest level of risks in Italy for 2022 and as the first bank group in Northern-Eastern Italy.

The data shown below are about 2022, in order to provide all the economic value in a temporary aligned and reliable way.

Current assets
(current resources to generate value)

763.607.554 €
39.8% of tot. assets
(+180.693.188€ compared to 2021)

Fixed assets

1.155.996.756 €
60% of tot. assets
(+51.617.522€ compared to 2021)

Accruals and deferrals (+)

5.068.126€
0.2% of tot. assets
(+1.897.094€ compared to 2021)

Credits for participation in the endowment fund

0€ (same in 2021)

Total assets
1.924.672.436€

Equity
878.051.890€
46% of liabilities+equity
(+35.773.311€ compared to 2021)

Debts
545.973.389€
28% of liabilities+equity
(+152.524.757€ compared to 2021)

Accruals and deferrals (-)
375.967.412€
19.5% of liabilities+equity
(+30.022.749€ compared to 2021)

Fund for risks and charges
114.507.457€
6% of liabilities+equity
(+14.245.402€ compared to 2021)

Severance pay
10.172.288€
0.5% of liabilities+equity
(+1.641.585€ compared to 2021)

Total liabilities+equity
1.924.672.436€

The whole Consolidated Financial Statement and its revision can be found following the links:

<https://www.sparkasse.it/en/investor-relations/financial-statements-and-reports/>

https://www.sparkasse.it/wp-content/uploads/SPK_Relazione-sullesercizio-2022_it_web_ES.pdf

CONSOLIDATED INCOME STATEMENT

The consolidated income statement **presents the financial performance of group companies** (i.e. parent and subsidiaries under common control) in one, single statement.

Here below, a focus on **positive and negative components for the characteristic management part.**

CONSOLIDATED PROFIT AND LOSS ACCOUNT	2022	2021
A) POSITIVE COMPONENTS OF MANAGEMENT		
Tax revenue	50.929.165	52.668.725
Income from equalisation funds	0	0
Income from transfers and contributions	138.676.750	155.272.444
<i>Current transfer income</i>	<i>128.033.618</i>	<i>143.095.344</i>
<i>Annual share of investment grants</i>	<i>9.954.612</i>	<i>11.702.891</i>
<i>Investment grants</i>	<i>688.520</i>	<i>474.209</i>
Revenue from sales and services and revenue from public services	855.137.298	494.587.424
Income from the management of assets	9.781.081	8.056.941
<i>Revenue from the sale of goods</i>	<i>19.139.682</i>	<i>12.594.120</i>
<i>Revenue and income from the provision of services</i>	<i>826.216.535</i>	<i>473.936.363</i>
Changes in inventories of work in progress, etc. (+/-)	554.843	2.582.865
Change in work in progress to order	20.729.279	4.149.137
Increases in fixed assets for internal works	29.909.827	31.113.122
Other miscellaneous income and income	37.317.562	46.066.137
total positive components of management A)	1.133.254.724	786.439.854
B) NEGATIVE COMPONENTS OF MANAGEMENT		
Purchase of raw materials and/or consumer goods	601.694.628	257.287.691
Provision of services	240.482.701	252.263.550
Use of third party assets	29.298.668	18.988.160
Transfers and subsidies	17.968.151	14.231.157
<i>Current transfers</i>	<i>14.803.383</i>	<i>13.593.312</i>
<i>Investment grants to other public administrations.</i>	<i>1.419.237</i>	<i>199.449</i>
<i>Investment grants to other entities</i>	<i>1.745.531</i>	<i>438.396</i>
Personal	131.777.763	133.342.047
Amortisation and depreciation of fixed capital	54.778.552	53.755.664
<i>Depreciation of fixed assets Intangible</i>	<i>12.649.030</i>	<i>11.568.488</i>
<i>Depreciation of tangible fixed assets</i>	<i>37.560.446</i>	<i>36.361.131</i>
<i>Other depreciation of fixed assets</i>	<i>485.416</i>	<i>872.667</i>
<i>Write-down</i>	<i>4.083.660</i>	<i>4.953.378</i>
Changes in inventories of raw materials and/or consumer goods (+/-)	-822.268	-1.597.941
Provision for risks	2.697.425	1.007.247
Other provisions	15.272.039	5.731.509
Miscellaneous operating costs	8.049.847	10.624.931
total negative components of operation B)	1.101.197.506	745.634.015
DIFFERENCE BETWEEN POSITIVE AND NEGATIVE COMP. OF MANAGEMENT		
(A-B)	32.057.218	40.805.839

Economic value generated and distributed

These data are taken from the Consolidated Income Statement, that can be found at the same link reported above (in the chapter about the "Declaration of Non-Financial Statement").

The Consolidated Income Statement describes which are the positive components (**credits**) and which are the negative ones (**debts**) for Bolzano's main bank group. The result of their difference is called "**economic value**". The financial capital are economic resources that the company has to carry out different activities. The different companies with large financial capital send their money directly to the stock exchange, to convert that capital into shares and thus generate greater profit.

Given the Group's operations and size, Sparkasse Group has not considered necessary to provide separate evidence to country, region, or market level. By the way, it's expressed how **Gruppo Alperia, Alto Adige Riscossioni SpA** and **Azienda Servizi Sociali Bolzano** have been distinguished, in terms of financial contribution, among all the shareholders.

Here below, the elements constituting the generated economic value, for 2020, 2021 and 2022. The voices are translated in English below the table with numerical data.

Valori in migliaia di euro - Dati consolidati		2022	2021	2020
10.	Interessi attivi e proventi assimilati	293.971	164.310	153.058
20.	Interessi passivi e oneri assimilati	-27.571	-14.947	-13.703
40.	Commissioni attive	123.012	97.658	87.378
50.	Commissioni passive	-8.146	-3.657	-4.284
70.	Dividendi e proventi simili	3.153	837	1.456
80.	Risultato netto dell'attività di negoziazione	4.898	1.505	629
90.	Risultato netto dell'attività di copertura	1.510	785	-490
100.	Utili (Perdite) da cessione o riacquisto di:	-305	28.916	9.277
	a) attività finanziarie valutate al costo ammortizzato	1.791	28.428	9.068
	b) attività finanziarie valutate al fair value con impatto sulla redditività complessiva	-2.110	492	365
	c) passività finanziarie	14	-4	-156
110.	Risultato netto delle attività e passività finanziarie valutate al fair value	-6.181	-4.090	-4.326
130.	Rettifiche/Riprese di valore nette per rischio di credito relativo a:	-43.126	-12.680	-14.504
	a) attività finanziarie valutate al costo ammortizzato	-42.892	-12.625	-14.878
	b) attività finanziarie valutate al fair value con impatto sulla redditività complessiva	-234	-55	374
140.	Utili/perdite da modifiche contrattuali senza cancellazioni	35	-54	-30
200 a.	Acc.ti netti ai fondi per rischi ed oneri - impegni e garanzie rilasciate	-3.084	1.950	-1.435
230.	Altri oneri/proventi di gestione	13.842	17.612	13.820
250.	Utili (Perdite) delle partecipazioni	833	384	0
280.	Utili (Perdite) da cessione di investimenti	2.761	2.443	33
320.	Utile (Perdita) delle attività operative cessate al netto delle imposte	-1.332	-400	-289
340.	Utile (perdita) d'esercizio di pertinenza dei terzi	3.242	0	0
A. TOTALE VALORE ECONOMICO GENERATO		356.679	280.188	280.188

- 10. Interest income and similar income
- 20. Interest expense and similar charges
- 40. Commissions receivable
- 50. Fees payable
- 70. Dividends and similar income
- 80. Net profit from trading
- 90. Net result from hedging activities
- 100. Gains (losses) on disposals and repurchases of:
 - a) Financial asset measured at amortised cost
 - b) Financial asset measured at fair value with impact on overall profitability
 - c) Financial liabilities
- 110. Net income from financial assets and liabilities measured at fair value
- 130. Net impairment losses/reversals related to:
 - a) Financial asset measured at amortised cost
 - b) Financial asset measured at fair value with impact on overall profitability

- 140. Gains (losses) from contract changes without cancellations
- 200. Net advances to provisions for risks and charges-Commitments for guarantees issued
- 230. Other operating expenses/income
- 250. Gains (losses) of shareholdings
- 280. Gains (losses) from the sale of investments
- 320. Gains (losses) of discontinued operations net of tax
- 340. Gains (losses) of the financial year pertaining to third parties
- A: TOTAL GENERATED ECONOMIC VALUE**

How is the economic value managed?

Sparkasse Group, Bolzano's saving banks, does not focus exclusively on profitability targets, but wishes to further strengthen **capital solidity** and improving the **risk liquidity profile** and the **innovation**.

An other goal is strengthening the **relations with all the stakeholders**, starting from the customers. For this reason, the company's **value added** (the difference between its total credits and its total debts for goods and services), is managed as described below.

- **83%** of the generated economic value is **distributed** in this way:
 - employees** receive part of the added value in the form of remuneration;
 - shareholders** expect an economic return on their financial resources committed to the company;
 - direct and indirect taxes converge to the **State**;
 - part of the money are invested for **social, cultural** and **environmental initiatives**.
- The remaining part (**17%**) is **withheld by the internal "business system"**, which obtains resources to be allocated to investments and daily operations to allow stability, economic growth and creation of new wealth.

Given the Group's operations and size, Sparkasse Group has not considered necessary to provide separate evidence to country, region, or market level.

Valore economico generato
(in milioni di euro)

Valore economico distribuito
(in milioni di euro)

Valore economico trattenuto
(in milioni di euro)

Generated economic value
(in millions of €)

=

distributed+withheld

Distributed economic value
(in millions of €)

83%

Withheld economic value
(in millions of €)

17%

It is shown in the figure above the **improvement over time** of the significant economic value generated and distributed, despite the significant increases in operating costs and investments intended for the expansion and modernization of the Group's business.

The economic performances of Bolzano's bank group are aligned to the European SDG number 8.

The graph shows the **distribution of economic resources in 2022**.

The main SDGs for which Bolzano invests are the warranty of a **decent work** and the **economic growth** (number 8, mentioned in the chart above), the **sustainability of cities and communities** (number 11), the **fight against the poverty** (number 1), the **reduction of inequalities** (number 10) and the investments on **industries, innovation and infrastructures** (number 9).

PUBLIC REVENUES AND EXPENDITURES

Data about public revenues and expenditures are available in the website: <https://www.altoadigeinnovazione.it/bolzano-bilancio-comune-2022/>.

The analysis of the public revenues and expenditures explains which is the provenience of the economic resources managed by Bolzano municipality, and which are the strategies to use these money.

Please, note that the budget has been impacted by the **Covid** emergency for 2022 (Numerical data are still uncertain) and by the reform of **IMI** for rented and vacant housing (expected to take effect in 2023).

Public Revenues:

For the main part, the incoming resources for Bolzano are **current revenues**. They amount to **€212.4 million**, of which:

-**€116.2 million from transfers;**

-**€49.7 million from non-tax revenue;**

-**€46.5 million from taxes** (45 million from IMI, for the ownership of real estate on the municipal territory).

The non-tax revenues derive from:

-the **management of assets (€13.3 million)**, as for social housing fees, parking, buildings, gas networks, cemetery;

-**€9 million from the sale of goods** (8.5 drugs);

-**€7.4 million from school fees, canteens, various services;**

-**€7.3 million from dividends** (Alperia €6.3 million and A22 €1.0 million);

-**€6.1 million from penalties for traffic violations;**

-**€6.7 million from VAT refunds.**

transfers	55%
taxes	22%
manag.assets	6%
sale o goods	4%
fees, other services	3,50%
dividends	3,40%
penalties	2,90%
VAT	3,10%

Public Expenditures:

Current expenses, so the daily expenses, amounted to **€211 million**, **investments** to **€133 million**.

Most of the current expenditure (**€92.3 million**) are used for **social aims**. The other main missions are:

- €44.1 million for **institutional services**;
- €17.2 million for **education**;
- €10.6 million for **economic development**;
- €10.3 million for **culture**.

Among the **capital expenditure** (investment spending on increasing fixed assets, for example, building a hospital, buying equipment or building a new road) the most significant item is that for **education** (**55.2 million**), then **mobility** (**44.9 million**).

Among the most significant **expected interventions**, the renovation works of the von Aufschneider school (23.734 million euros) and the Don Bosco retirement home (12.250 million).

CURRENT EXPENDITURES	
social aims	43,70%
institutional services	21%
education	8%
economic development	5%
culture	5%
other	17,30%

CAPITAL EXPENDITURES	
education	41,50%
mobility	34%
other	25%

The progressive decrease in the institution's **indebtedness** started in 2016 with the early repayment of mortgages.

- Today, the Municipality of Bolzano can take out new mortgages as long as the annual installment (principal + interest) does not exceed 1/3 of the current revenues of the last three years, which correspond to a loan of €1.2 billion.
- In the rest of Italy, the interest rate may not exceed 10% of current receipts, which corresponds to a loan of €750 million.

The graph shows how much Bolzano has been able to decrease its public debt.

PRODUCTIVE CAPITAL

The productive capital is the totality of infrastructure used for services as **public transportation**, **easy to monitor** (as maintenance), **professional** (carried on by operators) and **customized** services. In order to provide them, natural resources are exploited, so being focused on the **sustainability** is essential, especially nowadays.

The provincial government of Bolzano has projected about **50 missions** for the local infrastructures, to run within 2024. The main investments are: using about 106 million euros to finance various projects on the road network of South Tyrol, 75 million euros added through Danc (Debt authorized and not) for the bypass of Perca and 20.6 million euros of extraordinary funding for **road projects** ahead of the **2026 Winter Olympics**. Other works are also under way, including bypasses, new bridges and avalanche protection devices. These works provide many opportunities to find a job.

For more details, please consult <https://www.stradeeautostrade.it/notizie/2022/la-provincia-di-bolzano-conferma-il-programma-opere-pubbliche-del-2022-2024/>

Among the Italian cities, Bolzano is a leader for the sustainability. It has inaugurated the **first Italian public charging hub for cars**, built by Neogy, joint venture of Alperia and Gruppo Dolomiti Energia, in collaboration with Fiera Bolzano. 400 kW power stations allow you to recharge your car in a few minutes to travel a distance of 100 km, while the standard charging stations are designed for visitors to the fair or for those who want to leave their car for an extended period, for example to continue their journey by public transport. This way, Bolzano contributes concretely to reduce CO2 provided by both the Provincial Climate Plan, both from the Business Plan of our corporate group, since the stations of the new Hub are powered by green energy. In this case, it is partly produced on site thanks to the Fiera Bolzano photovoltaic system located directly above the charging hub.

The big goal is to become the most sustainable fair in Italy.

Further information are available following the link: <https://energiaoltre.it/elettrico-a-bolzano-il-primo-hub-italiano-di-ricarica-pubblica-per-auto/?v=1652d831a5cf62>

About public transportation and sustainability, Bolzano's students are carrying on a project aimed to implement a **unified subscription to travel freely throughout the Euregio**, an objective, the latter being pursued also with the students of the German-language consultations, Ladin and with the consultation of the students of Trentino and the representatives of Tyrol.

Furthermore, there are active projects to unify tourism and ecology. In fact, many **tours** of the local territory can be done **by train, bus, cableway or by bike**.

The excellent environmental programme sustained by Bolzano will go on also in the next years. Specifically, it has developed a comprehensive mobility system based on the integration of all transport mobility to ensure its environmental sustainability, in accordance with the Green New Deal and the new European Strategy for Sustainable and Intelligent Mobility. In addition to local public transport, the plan also includes bicycle mobility, the Brenner Digital Green Corridor, mobility management in sensitive areas, parking management and freight transport. The expectation is to realize it by 2035.

Digitisation also plays a central role in the new **#AltoAdigePlan**. For example, the payment of public transport and the booking of entire mobility packages will be further simplified. In addition, digitisation helps to recognise and understand traffic flows and thus to better control and address these mobility flows in sensitive areas such as the Dolomites. The goal is to ensure that the car is no longer the number one means of transport for the South Tyroleans. With regard to road infrastructure, the focus is on resilience. Supra-regional and transnational transport issues, such as the Brenner axis, are also reflected in the #AltoAdigePlan.

Information taken from: https://www.provincia.bz.it/turismo-mobilita/mobilita/trasporto-pubblico-locale/piano-provinciale-della-mobilita-sostenibile.asp?news_action=4&news_article_id=676434

Bolzano's economy is more diverse than industrial manufacturing alone. The region's economy benefits from **agriculture** (especially for apple orchards and vineyards), **woodworking** and **furniture manufacture, tourism, trade**, and services.

While it may not be a dominant manufacturing center like some other Italian cities, Bolzano plays a significant role in the regional and national economy due to its unique blend of industries and its strategic location.

Among the main customized services, we can list the tourism, in particular for the double language, **specialized healthcare** and **wellness offers, personalized business assistance** given by the Chamber of Bolzano, **transportation** services and also **waste management, housing assistance, and public safety services** for the citizens.

NATURAL CAPITAL

In 2020 the Municipality of Bolzano has obtained the highest level of ComuneClima certification, the program launched in 2016 by the CasaClima Agency to support and reward Municipalities that are committed to a sustainable energy policy and local development and which allows the evaluation of projects carried out in six sectors of intervention, relevant from an energy-environmental point of view. The South Tyrolean capital has thus officially become the first Gold Climate Municipality certified in Italy, after obtaining the Silver certification in 2018.

After the success achieved in 2021 with the achievement of the ComuneClima Gold certification, in June 2022 the Bolzano City Council decided to renew membership of the ComuneClima program for the next three years.

ComuneClima is the European program developed by the CasaClima Agency to accompany the Municipalities of Alto Adige in achieving the objectives established in the "Road Map Europa 2050" and in the "KlimaLand 2050 Strategy" and is based on the European "European Energy Award®" system already used by 1,346 Municipalities in Europe.

Within the ComuneClima program the following are analysed, evaluated and improved:

- energy and water consumption of buildings and municipal systems
- local energy production
- the concept of sustainable mobility
- waste management

[Click here to know more](#)

Sources:

<https://opencity.comune.bolzano.it/Novita/News/ComuneClima-anche-nel-triennio-2021-2023>

NATURAL CAPITAL

Available data relating to the city

	annual average µg/m ³	max value detected µg/m	exceedances of average limit daily	
			2020	2021
fine dust (pm10)	19	56	3	4
ozone (o3)	n.d.	155	0	0

waste collection · tons	2020	2021
total collection	51.488,4	53.061,6
waste sorting	34.098,7	35.061,7
Percentage of separated waste	66,2%	66,1%

water and gas consumption · m ³ / year	2020	2021
total water	8.333.458	8.068.202
total gas	78.418.541	83.499.184

Sources: Opuscolo Bolzano in cifre 2022

<https://opencity.comune.bolzano.it/Novita/Comunicati-stampa/Bolzano-in-cifre-2022>

SOCIAL CAPITAL

Social capital is described as the various levels of **citizens' participation** in the community reality, as with **innovative ideas** and **civic involvement**, but also with **moral values** as the tolerance and the equality. It is strictly connected to the human capital.

This capital is a valuable resource that can have a significant impact on personal well-being, community development, and societal cohesion.

There are different levels of these connections among Bolzano's citizens, the main concern the relationship between:

-Groups or communities (as families, local neighborhoods and cultural or religious groups), in the case of **bonding social capitals**.

-Different cultural and linguistic groups, since part of Bolzano's inhabitants are German mother tongue (with a tip of 100.00% in Martello), 26.06% Italian mother tongue (with a tip of 73.80% in Bolzano) and the remaining 4.53% Ladin mother tongue (with a tip of 97.66% in La Valle). There are **bridging social capitals** letting the cohesion among all these realities.

-Citizens and civic authorities, since we can see a high **civic engagement** that involves people actively participating in the decision-making processes of their community. In Bolzano, this could include involvement in local governance, volunteering for community organizations, and participation in public events and initiatives.

-**Community Organizations**, including nonprofits, clubs, and associations, can be indicative of social capital.

All these kinds of connection let having innovative **ideas**.

More in details, the municipality has organized meetings aimed to discuss about the main needs of the city and how to answer to them, with measures to take within 2025.

4 broad themes have been decided:

-**culture**: with representations balanced by gender and language, heterogeneous for interests and representation;

-**society**: analysis of social changes;

-**local territory**: mainly about public spaces, mobility, environment, energy, climate and aspects about the city;

-**economy and financial support**: analysis run by representatives of various professions to individuate the leading economic forces in Bolzano.

The main outcomes have been the projects listed in this chart, that in part have already taken place. By the way, citizens are involved through **competitions of ideas**, to propose new solutions. Note that the inhabitants are constantly updated through **appropriate informing centers**.

-For the territory, higher focus on public transports, especially with low emissions, new links with the industrial zone, more green areas, to organize an energy desk of the municipality with a site of information, higher use of rain and sun as energy resources and building of the ring road.

-For the culture, events and schools to emphasize the multilingualism, reduce the bureaucratic process regarding cultural associations through softwares, more social and cultural events, more focus on the tourism.

-The social initiatives are focused on volunteering, more services for family protection, migrants inclusion and elderly people, training courses, more security thanks to more police control and more public lighting.

-The economic side leaves the space to the creation of a centralized logistics center for the distribution of goods by non-polluting means, more chances to work for small companies using public infrastructures, more start-up incubators, a powerful city marketing, more efficacy in communicating municipality's ideas and more **financial support**, especially for families with little children, elderly members and in case of disability.

<https://economia.provincia.bz.it/it/sostegno-finanziario><https://opencity.comune.bolzano.it/Documenti-e-dati/Progetti-studi-e-ricerche/Idee-2025-Idee-per-lo-sviluppo-condiviso-della-Citta-di-Bolzano> to know more about it.

Picture representing citizens and migrants together to clean the city.

METHODOLOGICAL NOTE

This work was completed as part of the Public Management course at the SAA, University of Turin, under the supervision of Prof. Valerio Brescia. The elements presented in this assignment have been developed in accordance with the guidelines defined by Professors Paolo Biancone, Silvana Secinaro, Valerio Brescia, and Davide Calandra, by Elena Coppola (974648), Dajana Ferrara (1013893), Ariel Lo Cicero (974619).

The POP 2022 Budget is built with the intention of emphasizing some characteristics linked to the reference context and by consulting the official report documents and information published in the Municipality website and other institutional websites like Istat. All the websites have been linked close the related information given in the charts above. The following calculations of the percentages has been manually computed on the basis of the official collected data: NUMBER OF EMPLOYEES (FTE)-FUNCTIONS, DISTRIBUTION OF MAJOR AGE GROUPS, Users of ASSB, Consolidated Financial Statement, PUBLIC REVENUES AND EXPENDITURES.

Moreover we used graphs and images to better explain and highlight the data.

The POP 2022 Budget therefore aims to provide information and present data relating to the actions of the City and related companies, which are part of the local public group. Simple and accessible communication aims to stimulate a decision-making process extended to citizens through a reporting system that is publicly available.

DISSEMINATION PLAN

The results of the POP of Bolzano municipality will be published on facebook, on the scientific journal, on the official website of the municipality of Bolzano, Bozen.